

StarQuestAR: A mobile-based augmented reality application to learn concepts in astronomy

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Abstract—Immersive technologies are making their presence felt in various fields, including the education domain. Among the immersive technologies, Augmented Reality (AR) stands out as a powerful tool that seamlessly integrates virtual objects (3D) into the physical world, providing users with an interactive and engaging learning experience. AR-based contents can be accessed using mobile phones, which are widely available to the majority of the population. Due to its various advantages, AR has gained traction in the field of education. Recognizing the potential of immersive technologies, the Government of India, in its newly released National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, has proposed the integration of these technologies into educational institutions. However, despite this push, there is a scarcity of studies exploring the impact of AR technology specifically in the Indian educational context. To address this gap, we have developed AR-based learning content focused on the topic of the solar system, drawing from the textbook for class 6 issued by the National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT), an autonomous organization of the Government of India. To gauge the effectiveness of AR-based learning content, we conducted a pilot study utilizing Keller’s ARCS model, comparing the learning experience with that of traditional paper-based 3D models. The results of the study revealed that learners using AR-aided learning content exhibited higher levels of attention, relevance, confidence, and satisfaction. These findings demonstrate the potential of AR to enhance the educational experience for students. Additional research is necessary as it can provide valuable guidelines and recommendations for the successful adoption of AR technology within the Indian education context.

Index Terms—Augmented reality, Paper Based 3D- Model, Indian Education, Astronomy Education

I. INTRODUCTION

Dynamic learning environments using augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) can motivate students to actively construct knowledge. AR enhances the real world by overlaying digital content like text, graphics, and multimedia, providing an authentic learning experience. Studies have shown that AR technology positively impacts cognitive, motivational,

and social processes in education, improving problem-solving, critical thinking, and student motivation [3].

Integrating AR into the curriculum can create immersive and interactive learning environments, making learning more engaging and effective. However, designing and implementing AR learning activities require considering pedagogical aspects, user interaction, and content updates for teachers. While AR is gaining popularity, its application in educational research, especially in subjects like astronomy, remains limited.

The Government of India’s National Education Policy 2020 proposes integrating immersive technologies into educational institutions, but there is limited research on AR’s impact in the Indian context. To address this, the current study focuses on developing an AR application to teach astronomy concepts to high school students based on the NCERT textbook for class 6. The goal is to encourage discussion and creative expression to enhance student’s understanding and in-depth knowledge in the field of astronomy.

The current study compares the effectiveness of AR-based learning and the effectiveness of learning with paper-based 3D models using Keller’s ARCS model. This research also aims to explore the potential of AR in the Indian education system while learning abstract astronomical content by making the concepts easier and clearer to students through 3D visualization. The paper’s structure includes sections on related research, AR application design, methodology, pilot study results, and conclusions, acknowledging study limitations.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Studies have shown that the school curriculum has many subjects that require an understanding of abstract concepts and spatial representations and AR has the potential to provide valuable support to such subjects [6]. Further, in contrast to technologies like virtual reality, AR overlays computer-generated virtual imagery onto the real world, whether directly or indirectly, in real time [6]. Further, AR interfaces also maintain the same delivery of instructional content and only alter the way the content is comprehended by leveraging a distinctive combination of visual and sensory information [7].

Many studies have been conducted to understand the impact of AR in the teaching-learning process of different concepts. One of the studies focused on the development and use of an application named Augmented Reality Tracing (ART) aimed to engage children in the process of learning language writing by tracing over alphabets [8]. The results showed that the application provided a more engaging and interactive learning experience compared to traditional methods.

Salazar et al. [9] studied the effectiveness of an AR mobile application designed to educate fifth-grade students about the solar system. An experiment involving 27 students was conducted to study the impact of the AR application on the students. The results showed notable improvements in learning outcomes, user satisfaction, and overall interest in the subject. Xiao et al. [10] developed and analyzed the use of an AR based application to familiarize students with the planets in the solar system. The study involved 36 students, and the results indicated that the use of the AR application, combined with experiential learning, led to significant improvements in learning effectiveness, satisfaction, motivation, and overall interest in this learning approach.

The effectiveness of augmented books on students' learning and motivation was explored by Vahldick et al. [11]. A mobile AR application that presented interactive maps and other features related to the African continent was developed. The results of the study conducted among 28 ninth-grade students indicated a significant improvement in their average scores and increased motivation when using the AR application alongside the printed materials. Further, a study conducted by Turan et al.[12] indicated that the use of AR technology resulted in a decrease in students' cognitive load levels, while simultaneously improving their academic achievements and motivation. The results were based on a study involving the use of 15 AR applications among first-year university students to learn concepts in Geography.

To summarize, incorporating mobile-based AR technology in education offers several advantages, such as enhancing students' learning experience, increasing motivation, and promoting better knowledge retention. In addition, introducing new learning styles, especially in the fields of Geography and astronomy, allows students to visualize and comprehend abstract concepts and phenomena more effectively. However, despite the benefits observed, further research is needed to thoroughly assess the specific impact of mobile-based AR in Geography/Astronomy education and its overall effectiveness, especially in the context of the Indian Education system. Also, very little work has been done on comparing AR with non-AR methods. Hence, in this paper, we tried to cover these gaps through our research work by comparing the AR method with the non-AR (paper-based 3D models) method in Indian education.

III. DESIGN OF THE AR APPLICATION

To incorporate the learning content on the topic 'The Earth in the Solar System' found in the class 6 NCERT textbook issued by the Government of India, we created an AR-based

Fig. 1. Screenshot of the homepage of StarQuestAR application.

Fig. 2. Shows the 3D virtual images of the different celestial bodies

application 'StarQuestAR' using Unity 3D game engine and Vuforia SDK (a software development kit for smartphones). Computer vision is used by Vuforia to quickly and accurately identify three-dimensional objects. StarQuestAR is an android-based mobile augmented reality application. The app is designed as an active learning platform and a self-guided learning tool that allows the students to do self-study. In this app, the audio channel is also integrated along with the 3D models. StarQuestAR, which was developed as a marker-based AR application (Fig.1), uses the pictures present in the textbook as markers. The students use the app to detect the different images present in the textbook to display the corresponding 3D virtual image. They can interact with these virtual images and listen to the corresponding audio description about the celestial bodies.

The initial version of StarQuestAR has three main elements. The elements corresponding to an asteroid and the Moon allow the users to understand their shape and texture and provide options to rotate, drag, magnify, and shrink through the gesture

TABLE I
PARTICIPANT DETAILS

Group	Male	Female	Total
Paper Base 3D-Model	01	02	03
MAR	00	03	03
Total	01	05	06

TABLE II
MEAN VALUE FOR ARCS FACTOR

Factors	Paper Based	MAR	Percentage Difference
Attention	16.3	18.6	13.18 increase
Relevance	16.6	18.6	11.36 increase
Confidence	16.6	19	13.48 increase
Satisfaction	17.3	18.3	5.61 increase
Overall	66.3	74.6	11.78 increase

Fig. 3. Experimental Procedure

of touch (Fig.2). Through the audio option, the students can listen to the different features of each planet. Before conducting the pilot study with end-users, it was ensured that the application was stable and followed the required functional requirements as per the curriculum.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Participants

In this pilot study, six students of grade 6, around 11 years voluntarily participated. All the students used NCERT textbooks as part of their curriculum. Before conducting the study, the participants were detailed about the objectives of the study. The participants were randomly divided into two groups: the traditional Paper based -3D Model group and the Mobile Augmented Reality (M-AR) - based group as mentioned in Table I.

B. Data collection and instrument

The effectiveness of both methods was compared using Keller's ARCS Model. A questionnaire comprising 16 questions was prepared related to Attention, Relevance, Confidence, and Satisfaction on a Likert scale of 1-5. Here, "1" corresponds to "Strongly Disagree," and "5" corresponds to "Strongly Agree".

C. Experimental procedure

Before initiating the study, an introductory lecture on the solar system was given to all the participants. The participants were then randomly assigned to two groups. One group interacted with traditional paper-based 3D models of the celestial objects and the other group interacted through the developed StarQuestAR application. The details of the AR app were explained to the students and they used the application installed on an Android-based mobile phone. Using the prepared questionnaires, both groups were compared on the basis of Attention, Relevance, Confidence, and Satisfaction using Keller's ARCS model (Fig.3.). Qualitative feedback on the AR app was also sought from teachers who teach these topics in their regular classes.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The empirical data were analyzed by the method followed by Khan et.al [5]. The Cronbach's alpha of the survey questionnaire was determined to be 0.82, showing good internal consistency of the questionnaire. The mean values were calculated for both the questionnaires for the four factors that measured student motivation based on the ARCS model [13]. The mean value for each ARCS factor was calculated as shown in Table II. The percentage differences indicate that the mean values for attention, relevance, confidence, and satisfaction increased.

The data collected through the questionnaire based on Keller's ARCS model showed that the students were found to be more confident and satisfied in interacting with AR-based content as compared to traditional paper-based 3D models. However, more statistical analysis is required to determine the significance of the change in the mean value for each ARCS factor.

Based on the interaction with students, it was found that even though the participants were using AR for the first time, the application appeared to be easy to use. They interacted with the virtual images of the celestial bodies and listened to the respective audio descriptions. The students' fascination was evident as they interacted with the real-time 3D model, particularly when exploring the asteroid. Their feedback emphasized that the AR application significantly improved their visualization of the asteroid's shape. The captivating nature of the 3D model and its ability to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the asteroid's characteristics showcased the potential of AR technology as an effective tool for enhancing students' comprehension and engagement in the study of celestial objects. These observations shed light on the positive impact of AR applications in astronomy education, promoting a deeper connection with complex concepts and fostering a sense of excitement and curiosity among learners.

In the course of our study, we observed a notable level of enthusiasm and interest among the students when engaging with the educational app. In fact, one student went as far as inquiring about the source to download the app, expressing a strong desire to continue learning through this medium.

The incorporation of AR into their textbooks further fueled their excitement, as they eagerly embraced the interactive and immersive learning environment. These findings highlight the potential benefits of using AR technology in education.

Apart from gathering data from the students, we also presented the AR application to teachers who were responsible for teaching these topics using traditional methods in their regular classes. While many teachers appreciated the concept of augmented reality, they also expressed apprehensions regarding its implementation in classrooms. One teacher even appealed to still use paper-based 3D models, as they offer a more tangible and interactive experience for students. However, the teacher also acknowledged the challenges of creating physical models for every topic, as it requires significant time and effort from educators. Additionally, the teachers, who were already utilizing 2D animation videos in their teaching, were uncertain about how to effectively incorporate AR into their lessons, and the potential for distraction in the classroom was also a point of consideration. These insights highlight the need for further research and support in addressing the practical concerns and exploring the best practices for integrating AR technology in educational settings effectively.

VI. CONCLUSION

The aim of this study was to examine how an AR-based mobile application enhances the student's attention and confidence in learning certain topics in astronomy in the context of the Indian Education System as compared to the non-AR paper-based model. Existing literature highlights the lack of sufficient research on the use of mobile AR in education, presenting an opportunity to explore the potential benefits of AR in enhancing students' learning through visualization and ultimately contributing to improved academic performance. Our study demonstrated that students' attention, relevance, confidence, and satisfaction levels were higher when using AR than the paper-based model, indicating the effectiveness of introducing AR in Indian school education, aligning with the objectives of NEP2020. Looking ahead, integrating other technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), machine learning, and artificial intelligence (AI) with AR-based learning systems and more elements of gamification could further enhance the development of effective and futuristic learning platforms. However, more research is needed to address the practical challenges and explore optimal strategies to effectively integrate AR technology in educational settings, catering to the diverse needs of students and educators alike.

VII. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

The present study focused on only sixth-grade students and a specific topic, restricting the generalizability of the findings. The AR application's functionality is limited to the images (markers) provided in the NCERT textbook, which may affect its broader applicability. Additionally, statistical analysis to determine the significance of changes in mean values for each ARCS factor could not be conducted. Future research should aim to include a more diverse student population to

ensure broader applicability. Due to limited resources, the experiment's duration was short, suggesting the potential for longer-term follow-up studies.

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